

MASTER'S PROGRAMME
IN DIGITAL METHODS FOR THE HUMANITIES

**Encoding of Ancient Greek Mathematical Texts with
the TEI standard; the case of Euclid's Elements**

MASTER'S THESIS

DIMITRA GRIGORIOU

ATHENS, OCTOBER 2022

ATHENS UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS
DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATICS
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Supervisor: Professor Dr. Papatheodorou

Examination

Committee:

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Abstract

The emergence of Digital Humanities as a field of study has created the need for a standardized format for encoding manuscripts and typescripts. The TEI standard provides this solution for written texts. In this project, a particular focus is placed on the encoding of mathematical structures and expressions found in ancient Greek mathematical texts. The TEI standard is investigated and used for encoding texts - of mathematical works of ancient Greek literature and in particular Euclid's first book of elements. An attempt is made to compare different approaches to creating digital editions of Euclid's Elements with or without the use of TEI, taking into account the original text and its translation into other languages (e.g., English). The different encoding methods and the comparison between them will highlight the requirements for encoding texts that are not covered by the TEI standard. Suggestions will be made to close this gap in TEI.

Keywords: *text encoding, mathematical texts, Euclid's Elements, TEI, digital publication, digital humanities*

Περίληψη

Η ανάδειξη των ψηφιακών ανθρωπιστικών επιστημών ως τομέα μελέτης δημιούργησε την ανάγκη για έναν τυποποιημένο μορφότυπο για την κωδικοποίηση χειρογράφων και δακτυλογραφημένων κειμένων. Το πρότυπο TEI παρέχει αυτή τη λύση για τα γραπτά κείμενα. Σε αυτό τη μεταπτυχιακή διατριβή, δίνεται ιδιαίτερη έμφαση στην κωδικοποίηση μαθηματικών δομών και εκφράσεων που απαντώνται σε αρχαία ελληνικά μαθηματικά κείμενα. Το πρότυπο TEI διερευνάται και χρησιμοποιείται για την κωδικοποίηση κειμένων - μαθηματικών έργων της αρχαίας ελληνικής γραμματείας και ειδικότερα του πρώτου βιβλίου στοιχείων του Ευκλείδη. Γίνεται προσπάθεια σύγκρισης διαφορετικών προσεγγίσεων για τη δημιουργία ψηφιακών εκδόσεων των Στοιχείων του Ευκλείδη με ή χωρίς τη χρήση του TEI, λαμβάνοντας υπόψη το πρωτότυπο κείμενο και τη μετάφρασή του σε άλλες γλώσσες (π.χ. αγγλικά). Οι διαφορετικές μέθοδοι κωδικοποίησης και η μεταξύ τους σύγκριση θα αναδείξουν τις απαιτήσεις για την κωδικοποίηση κειμένων που δεν καλύπτονται από το πρότυπο TEI. Θα γίνουν προτάσεις για να καλυφθεί αυτό το κενό στο συγκεκριμένο πρότυπο.

Λέξεις κλειδιά: κωδικοποίηση κειμένου, μαθηματικά κείμενα, Στοιχεία του Ευκλείδη, TEI, ψηφιακή δημοσίευση, ψηφιακές ανθρωπιστικές επιστήμες

To every single person who supports me and believes in me ...

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1. Introduction

1.1 Defining subject matter

Over the past two decades, in the context of the development of information technology for the humanities (humanities computing), there has been considerable effort in the creation of data encoding standards and text management tools for the humanities. These efforts aim to meet the information-seeking needs of researchers in the relevant scholarly field by creating usable and easily accessible electronic collections. The scientific community has an increased and specific need for access, search, and retrieval of information, as users' interest is primarily focused on biographies and writings, syntactical, factual, and etymological annotations. In addition to scholars, libraries have long been interested in encoding texts in response to the proliferation of proprietary file formats introduced by mass-market software (Gannetti 2019:1). Scholars, technicians, and information specialists all expressed the need for a standardized and application-independent method of representing literary and historical texts for the computer age.

One of the most useful means for editing and managing collections of humanities content is the "electronic text" (Hockey 2000:1). The term primarily refers to the encoding of a text rather than its electronic or digital representation. Markup languages have been used to achieve electronic or digital representation. Markup languages, in fact, are used for the creation, structured representation, and processing of electronic text. The first markup language that was used for the creation of electronic documents is the Standard Generalized Markup Language or SGML. SGML is a language that defines hardware- and software-independent methods for representing texts in electronic form and encodes their content and structure. SGML gave rise to HyperText Markup Language, or HTML for short, which is widely used on the Internet. The possibilities of HTML are limited because, although it is easy to use, it only represents the visual aspect of the text and not its actual content. Extensible Markup Language (eXtensible Markup Language - hereafter XML), which is considered a simpler version of SGML, was developed because of the difficulty in learning and using SGML and the superficiality of HTML. The term "meta-markup languages" refers to SGML and XML that can be used to construct new vocabularies and markup languages. Because of their unique properties and the organized syntax, they provide, SGML and XML

have served as a solid foundation for the development of encoding and data standards in a variety of scientific disciplines, including the humanities. In this project, however, the focus is exclusively on a "dialect of XML" (Fusi 2022) called the Text Encoding Initiative, or TEI, which is being used with the goal of encoding the original version of Euclid's Elements books in the ancient Greek version.

Euclid's books have always been a source of research for international libraries, as they provide a rich basis for various projects. Some of them are the "Perseus Project", "Byrne's Euclid", "Digilib Project", the "Claymath Project", etc. On these websites, users can find the original and English version of the book in parallel, along with images of the original text. Some projects, such as the Perseus project, also provide the XML version of the text for further study depending on research needs. However, most published projects on TEI and literary texts rarely deal with mathematical texts as a product of encoding, certainly not when the texts are in ancient Greek. In other words, these texts are not treated nor investigated, at least to my knowledge, as a means of information extraction and association, rather than as a means of cultural preservation and documentation. Schiefsky (2007:1) hopes that the advent of innovative technologies can provide new viewpoints for the study of primary sources in the history of science and mathematics. The new technologies could make it easier for researchers to investigate long-standing problems in novel ways and to address new questions that are difficult to answer using traditional research methods (Schiefsky 2007:1). This is why this project attempts to encode the ancient Greek version of Euclid's First Book of Elements, and in particular the propositions, by emphasizing the content (i.e., terms, enunciations, proofs, names, etc.) as the target of the transcription. In a second step, a series of suggestions, adjustments, and possible changes in the TEI module were made to highlight the content and interaction of the elements of the text. In the last step, an attempt would be made to jot down guidelines where concise methods of encoding mathematic text would be presented with the hope of using it as a yardstick for future research.

1.2 Structure of the Thesis

The present project is divided into two main components: the theoretical part and the methodological part. In the first part, the historical development of TEI is presented. In particular, the development of the text encoding initiative and the creation of the current guidelines are discussed. This section also briefly introduces the main components of a TEI document, highlighting and appreciating how they differ from a typical XML document. The transition from previous encoding methods (e.g., SGML) is addressed, as well as the reason why TEI has become a popular tool for those involved in digital philology or digital humanities in general. In this part, there would also be a brief introduction to Euclid's life and his work "Elements" and why the coded version is important for future researchers.

In the second part of the research, the methodology will be presented. More specifically, the editor used to code the document will be mentioned, as well as the decisions made during the coding of the text. In addition, gray areas and moments of uncertainty during the digitization process of the document would be addressed as they would facilitate further future research. In addition, the limitations of the project are also highlighted, as it is an experimental approach to encoding a scientific text. Finally, an analysis of the results is presented, followed by possible suggestions and further research points worth exploring.

2. Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)

2.1 Data encoding

From the first attempt of Father Roberto Busa S.J.'s (Busa, [1965]; 1976, 1997) with the "Index Thomisticus" in 1949 including lemmatized concordance lines of Thomas Aquinas and Michael West's (1953) "General Service List" the need of systematizing and presenting knowledge and data was more important than ever. The use of computers has drastically changed and improved the quality of research. Computing techniques have facilitated and shortened processes by providing a set of tools. Numerous theories, tools, and methods have been developed that focus on data capture and entry through digitization, image processing, and OCR; text analysis through concordance formation, sorting, text representation and retrieval, lemmatization, statistical analysis, and online exchange are some of the possibilities offered in the new researchers. Therefore, in order to apply the techniques mentioned above, systems should be developed to allow computer systems to process the data entered. Michael Sperberg-McQueen (1991: 34) aptly puts his understanding of how computers understand and process external data:

"Computers can contain and operate on patterns of electronic charges, but they cannot contain numbers, which are abstract mathematical objects not electronic charges, nor texts, which are complex, abstract cultural and linguistic objects."

The need of inventing a system that would be reliable and cater to "reusability, interchange, system- and software-independence, portability, and collaboration" in the humanities (Vanhouette 2004) was an absolute necessity and eventually covered by the arrival of the Standard Generalized Markup Language (SGML) which became an ISO standard in 1986 (ISO 8879:1986) (Goldfarb, 1990). Such markup language fulfilled a large number of the needs expressed by academia (Barnard et al., 1988: 28-29); SGML is comprehensive; it is simple to use; it is able to process documents thanks to its moderate complexity software design; SGML is independent of any particular feature set or input device; this standard allows users to describe a text and edit it if needed; SGML enables researchers the exchange of encoded texts across communication networks. The advent of such standard was what

researchers and the humanities in particular to pursue the preparation and interchange of electronic documents amongst each other.

2.2 A brief history: Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange

Libraries have long been interested in the work of the text encoding community, which emerged in the late 1980s as a protest against the overabundance of proprietary file formats made available by mainstream software. This problem of data restoration, preservation and readability by any machine was tackled in the spring of 1987. Humanities scholars were primarily responsible for the development of what would become the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange, and librarians were also quick to recognize the benefits of a standard that would give them some control over the selection and distribution of electronic texts for the scholarly community (Gaunt 1999; Hockey 2004). Early library involvement in this high-profile branch of the digital humanities was primarily focused on technical services related to digitization, metadata, and preservation. Therefore, the scope of TEI ends up providing the ability to create, exchange and integrate textual data in digital form, in every kind of text, in every language for any purpose from any culture. Although text encoding is not the same as digital editing, anyone beginning an editorial effort must decide whether or not to follow the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative. Because the TEI provides a toolkit for thinking about the implications of representing text digitally, and a way to make one's thoughts clear through markup, it has become the norm for creating machine-readable text for humanistic studies (Burnard, 2014; Pierazzo, 2015b).

Most projects concerned with the electronic capture and representation of texts and other linguistic data prior to the creation of the TEI developed their own encoding schemes, usually limited to the data for which they were intended. The TEI provided coding conventions based on this to describe the physical and logical structure of many classes of text, as well as features specific to a particular text type or not typically represented in typography. The TEI guidelines also address problems of conventional text encoding, such as overlapping hierarchies, arbitrary delineation of text segments, alignment of parallel elements, and cross-referencing within and between texts. They also provide protocols for linking texts with audio and visual data. In fact, TEI was the first system that intended to provide recommendations and practice which was usable both by beginners in the field of text encoding but also on the other hand people who were expert and wanted to experiment on

things that had not been tried before. Thus, the TEI motivated and completed the extensive intellectual task of completing this analysis for a large number of text types.

2.3 From SGML to TEI

Most humanities resources are in text form, which underscores the need to create standards and management tools for this genre. Humanities texts are complex, written in a foreign language (e.g., ancient Greek, Latin, etc.) and contain a great deal of data that must be encoded in the best possible way to improve search and retrieval of information. Their complexity lies in large part in the number of different types of information they contain, the text forms they can combine (e.g., poetry combined with prose, or a play combined with poetry) but also the way the texts are written based on the level of language. In theory TEI can cope with any texts of any size language, date complexity, writing system or media, such as books, journals, posters, rolls of papyrus, etc.

The international Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) standard came to provide a suitable solution for the encoding and exchange of texts in the Humanities. More specifically the TEI takes a general and agnostic approach to textual structure and verbal phenomena written or spoken. Concerning the textual structure, it is based on codex format whereas it is also applicable to non-codex material. The verbal stuff is mostly suitable for linguistics, however, there are general-purpose interpretative tags that can be employed as well. The TEI is published and supported by the TEI Consortium, which produces sets of rules and guidelines for the processing and exchange not only of texts relating to the Humanities (e.g., theatrical plays, poetry, historical artifacts) but also those relating to the wider linguistic industry (e.g., printed dictionaries). The TEI was conceived from the beginning as a set of building blocks for the development of a scheme suitable for a particular purpose. (Bondar and Flanders, 2011). This is consistent with the concept of the TEI, which emphasizes providing readers with a vocabulary for characterizing texts rather than prescribing in detail what they should or should not contain. This suggests that “it is *likely*, not just *possible*, that you will want to have a tailored view of the TEI” (TEI Consortium 2022). Versions of the standard are expressed in SGML, with the most recent (TEI P5) offering “One Document Does it All” (ODD).

TEI is one of the data encoding standards used primarily in the library and archival environment which were the ones that create the TEI guidelines for encoding and interchange. The flexibility of TEI guidelines is both a great strength and a potential obstacle. TEI is

primarily a descriptive data encoding standard but is also classified as a descriptive, administrative, and structural metadata standard (DLC/BAER Metadata Group 3, 2002). Descriptive because it describes sources for the purpose of retrieval and identification of information, and administrative because it provides the knowledge about the management of a source, e.g., when and by whom it was created, technical details, information about the management of a source, information about the source, and information about the source itself access information, etc. (Boudouri 2019:4). Since 2002 TEI is based on XML and thus following its convention (i.e., tree structure: a single root and many descendent nodes). It has a more content-oriented approach and more restrictive syntax. Finally, the TEI is also one of the standards for encoding structural metadata, as it specifies how the items in a document are combined and presented to the audience, e.g., the arrangement of pages into chapters, the number of lines in poems, etc. (Hodge 2001:3). In general, TEI serves the encoding of written literally texts with the aim of preserving and highlighting as much information as possible depending – of course – on the needs of the project.

Figure 1: The evolution of markup languages. Venice Virtual Summer Camp, 2020

2.4 The structure of a valid TEI document

Like any other markup language, TEI is subject to a set of guidelines that provide a standard so that data with a particular format can be easily exchanged. To achieve this, researchers must follow a set of rules designed by the TEI Consortium, also known as TEI-C, when encoding written documents in this format. In this way, TEI provides structural guidance for researchers to achieve consistency when encoding a text. Consistency in terms of formatting allows researchers to represent all kinds of features of all texts in a universal way. In this respect, TEI becomes an accessible tool for encoding and exchanging data while being program-independent, since it is strongly based on the XML markup language.

The following figure (i.e., Figure 1) shows a simple structure of what a valid TEI encoding looks like. In the first half of the module (i.e., from `<TEI>` to `</teiHeader>`) you will find information about the type of resource, such as digital or analog text, author, publication, publisher, and so on. To be more specific, there is the root `<TEI>` element that points to the TEI-C's XML namespace. Secondly, the root is followed by the `<teiHeader>` which includes important metadata regarding the document. These metadata must encompass the `<fileDesc>` element, which contains a description of the file. Within the `<fileDesc>` element, there are a few elements nested; namely, the `<titleStmt>` containing a `<title>`, `<author>`, and any information about other contributors related to this document, such as `<editor>` element; a publication statement (i.e., `<publicationStmt>`) which would provide publication details about the electronic text in a structured manner or as prose inside a paragraph element (i.e., `<p>`); a source description element (i.e., `<sourceDesc>`) which is the bibliographic details about the electronic text's material source in a structured fashion or inside a `<p>` element. The second part of the TEI structure is crucial and important because the characteristics may differ between different editions of the same text. In the second half of the scheme (i.e., from `<text>` to `</body>`), the coding of the text begins. The third part of the document begins with a `<text>` element; this is a general text element that contains the `<body>` of the text or the `<front>` matter, the `<back>` matter or usually a combination of two or three of those elements. Within these three structural divisions, there are other subdivisions often encoded with `<div>` elements. In these `<div>` elements type attributes elements are nested which specify what type of division is presented. Depending

on the given information or the needs of the research, the researcher uses the appropriate set of tags to mark the appropriate information. The fragments of DTD, which is defined as the “vocabulary and the syntax of a markup language” (Vanhouette 2004), vary depending on the type of text to be encoded and the features to be pointed out. Apart from the "Core Tag Sets" and the "Basic Tag Sets" (Ida 2000), which are essential for identifying and classifying the text during the coding process, the "Additional Tag Sets" are optional and depend on the research. TEI's elements are case-sensitive, and the start and end tag must match. Most projects only require about 25 elements in total from the 570 elements and 200 attributes offered by the TEI. All in all, it can be stated that the TEI was developed to help researchers deepen their research.

On the other hand, there exists a significant population of individuals who hold a skeptical perspective regarding the organization and preservation of data within the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI). The reason is the loss of information or important features during the digitization process and the inability to create a copy worthy of the original. Resistance to the technical complexity of TEI also remains a barrier to adoption. For this reason, those who deal with text encoding in their daily work are often more willing to adopt it. These include archivists skilled in encoded description of archives, all types of digital librarians working in the library, and metadata librarians (EAD). Given the academic or historical expertise and computer skills required to create, publish, and maintain an online digital edition, collaboration between subject matter experts and IT specialists is often recommended (Pierazzo, 2015b). However, if one expands the definition of collaboration to include both synchronous and diachronic collaboration, various arrangements are conceivable. Despite the criticism that TEI faces whether the primary goals and scopes are achieved by using the TEI will be discussed in the following chapters.

```
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <teiHeader>
    <fileDesc>
      <titleStmt>
        <title><!--Title--></title>
      </titleStmt>
      <publicationStmt>
        <p><!--Publication Information--></p>
      </publicationStmt>
      <sourceDesc>
        <p><!--Information about the source--></p>
      </sourceDesc>
    </fileDesc>
  </teiHeader>
  <text xml:id="text1">
    <body>
      <p>This is the first paragraph</p>
    </body>
  </text>
</TEI>
```

Figure 2: Basic declarations as provided by Edward Vanhoutte & Ron Van den Branden (2019:9)

2.5 TEI DTD (P5)

In the year 2000 a set of concrete guidelines were published so that this new governance structure for the TEI, reorganized as a membership consortium, could be a roadmap to address concerns regarding the structure and encoding of documents with the use of TEI. In 2002 with the Proposal 4 (P4) version there has been a change in the entire expression format of the system from SGML to XML; no attempt was made to remove or change much that may be considered outdated, nor to address any of the several new areas of digital activity where the TEI method might be useful or relevant, as “backwards compatibility” was an explicit design priority for that release (Burnard 2020). As the prologue to P4 states, an informed and engaged TEI Council is essential to guide and approve such enhancement and maintenance efforts in response to the changing needs and priorities of the TEI user community. The major accomplishment of the TEI Consortium over the past five years has been the establishment and management of the activities of this Technical Council and its companion Working Groups. The result of this effort was the publication of TEI Proposal 5 (P5), the subsequent final edition of the Guidelines, in October 2007.

The following passage contains a summary of the decisions taken on these issues at the first meeting of WP3 in Copenhagen on 28 February 2007 and presented on the website of the University of Oxford¹:

A. Content model changes

1. In TEI P5 components with special characteristics could be introduced within the same paragraph as a paragraph that can be considered as `macro.specialPara`. The distinction is that the content of the element does not require the introduction of a `<p>` element.

```
<accMat>Pastedown on  
fols 2 and 4</accMat>
```

Elements with this content model

are: `<accMat>`, `<acquisition>`, `<additions>`, `<collation>`, `<condition>`,

¹ You may visit the website here: <http://projects.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/Deliverables/WP3-00.1.0.xml?splitLevel=-1>

- <custEvent>, <decoNote>, <foliation>, <layout>, <musicNotation>, <origin>, <provenance>, <source> and <surrogates>. However, the element <watermarks> which had also this content model has been eliminated.
2. In TEI P5, the direct references to within all such content models have been revised to refer to the `model.pLike` element classes. This makes it possible to use either or in a TEI P5 module, if available; or to define other generic elements for use here.
 3. The following elements, all of which had PCDATA content models, now in TEI P5 they have a content model of `macro.xText: <msName>` (formerly `<altname>`), `<collection>`, `<depth>`, `<height>`, `<institution>`, `<locus>`, `<origDate>`, `<origPlace>`, and `<repository>`, as well as `<width>`. This modification makes it possible to represent nonstandard characters or alternative glyphs in otherwise simple text using the TEI P5 `<g>` element.
 4. In P5, the `<msHeading>` element has been replaced by a generic `<head>` element that includes most, but not all, of the child elements previously allowed within `msHeading`. In particular, it does not allow `<author>`, `<respStmt>`, or `<textLang>`, but a large number of phrase-level elements are allowed. In addition, the Manuscriptorium article on technical compatibility of metadata suggests that `<msHeading>` should include at least `<title>`, `<author>`, `<origdate>`, `<textLang>`, and (optionally) `<note>`, among other criteria about basic compatibility requirements. Nevertheless, this is not required by DTD.
 5. The following is a list of further content model differences:
 - The TEI P5 `<dimensions>` element may only include one or zero `<height>`, `<width>`, and `<depth>` components, respectively, as opposed to any number of them in any particular order.
 - The element `<accMat>` is no longer a child of `<additional>`, but rather one of its siblings.
 - The element `<remarks>` within `<adminInfo>` is swapped by a reference to the class `model.notelike`.
 - The element `<overview>` is not allowed in the `<bindingDesc>` section. `<p>` elements will be created from its contents if one is given.

- The element `<summary>` is used in place of the element `<overview>` when it is included in `<msContents>`
- When the element `<langUsage>` comes inside a `<msItem>`, `textLang` takes its place.
- When the element `<q>` exists within the element `<msItem>`, the element `<quot>` is substituted; another option is `<cit>`, which groups a quote with an attribution.
- An optional `<textlang>` element may be present in the `<msContents>` element.
- As an alternative to `<msItem>`, a new element called `<msItemStruct>` might show up in `<msContents>`.
- Instead of an inclusive alternation of model.pLike elements with `<handNote>` (formerly `<handDesc>`) elements, the `<handDesc>` (formerly `<msWriting>`) element now contains one.
- The optional specialist elements (`<overview>` and `<watermarks>`) that the `<support>` included have been removed in favor of a simpler content model (`macro.specialPara`).

B. Renamed elements

At TEI P5, a few items underwent name changes. They're listed in the following table:

Old name (P4 version)	New name (P5 version)	Comments
<code>msDescription</code>	<code>msDesc</code>	"desc" is used as a suffix throughout P5
<code>altName</code>	<code>msName</code> or <code>altIdentifier</code>	In Master, the term <code><altname></code> is used for "alternate name" and "alternative identifier, but the terms now are separated in P5.

decoration	decoDesc	For consistency
handDesc	handNote	For consistency
overview	summary	only within msContents
msWriting	handDesc	For consistency
msHeading	head	
idno (at the beginning of msPart)	altIdentifier	other uses for idno remain unchanged

C. Additional elements

- The reworking of the MASTER <physDesc> element resulted in the addition of several new elements, including <objectDesc>, <supportDesc>, <sealDesc>, and <layoutDesc>. The new element <supportDesc> now contains the previous <support>, <extent>, <foliation>, <collation>, and <condition> elements that were once direct children of <physDesc>. The new grouping element <layoutDesc> now encloses the preexisting <layout> element. These two components, along with <accMat>, <additions>, <bindingDesc>, <decorDesc> (formerly decoration), <handDesc>, <musicNotation>, and the new <sealDesc> element, now make up the new <objectDesc> element, a child of <physDesc>.
- When this comes at the beginning of a <msPart> element, a new <altIdentifier> element takes the place of <idno>.
- As an alternative to <msitem>, a new <msItemStruct> element is now available; it has the same child elements but limits their order and cardinality.

D. Removed elements

- TEI P5 does not contain the MASTER components <overview>, <paratext>, <remarks>, or <watermarks>. All of these ought to be changed with the <p> element.

- In TEI P5, the element `<form>` is no longer present in the manuscript module (there is a TEI element of this name in the dictionary module). The new `<objectDesc>` element's `@form` attribute fulfills its purpose.

E. Important attribute changes

There are some changes to the globally accessible characteristics at TEI P5. Each aspect is impacted by these modifications. Some key changes that are relevant to this project are:

- `@id` becomes `@xml:id`
- `@lang` turns into `@xml:lang` and must be specified with a valid language identifier
- `@rendition` is available as a more focal option to `@rend`
- `@TEIform` is not used anymore
- TextLang's `@langKey` attribute has been renamed to `@mainLang`. Now that it and `@otherLangs` have values, they adhere to the same restrictions as `@xml:lang`
- A new module in TEI P5 enables extremely thorough and consistent labeling of place and personal names and the occasions and things associated with them. As a result, several of the properties used in MASTER have changed. In particular, for `<name>`, `<country>`, `<institution>`, etc. `@key` is renamed to `@ref` and refers to a `<person>` or `<place>` element, depending on the context. For such an entity, a new `@key` attribute is used to provide an encoded value (as an alternative). These elements no longer support `@full`, `@reg`, and `@role` properties. For `<origPlace>`, `@reg` is also not available.
- In TEI P5, `@unit` is replaced by `@units`, `@scope` is retained, and a new property `@quantity` can be used to indicate the actual measure instead of it being part of the element's content.

F. The DTD Manuscriptorium

Currently, the manuscriptorium DTD combines three DTD parts:

- a) MASTER components, which were discussed in the previous paragraph of this document.
- b) about 150 additional TEI elements, mainly from the Core, Header, and Names and Dates modules.

- c) Some (302, but not all) of the 302 foreign components appear to perform the same functions as existing TEI elements.

3. Euclid as the father of Geometry

The laws of nature are but the mathematical thoughts of God – Euclid

Euclid was a Greek mathematician who lived in this great Hellenistic age of science. He was born about 330 B.C. and died in 275 or 270 B.C. Little is known about Euclid's life, and of it little is documented or verified. According to Proclus, he lived in the time of Ptolemy I of Egypt (323 - 285 BC) - therefore he was older than Eratosthenes and Archimedes.

Some say Euclid was born in Sicily and others in Tyre. He studied in Athens, at the Academy of Plato, where he was distinguished for his mathematical works. For this reason, the King of Egypt, Ptolemy I, invited him to Alexandria to teach Arithmetic and Geometry at the famous educational institution called “Museion”s (Vardoulakis et al. 2016) (Figure 3). The foundation of the mathematical school of Alexandria is also attributed to him; thus, Euclid is known as Euclid of Alexandria. His work leads us to the conclusion that Euclid was an excellent teacher (Argiroupolos et al. 2015). He presented the principles of mathematics in such a way that they could be understood by his contemporaries and later student-scholars. Most of his work was not original but included the work of earlier mathematicians such as Thales of Miletus (c. 623 - c.545 B.C), which he systematized in a scientific way. Thus, Euclid made mathematics more accessible. Except for mathematics and geometry, Euclid wrote books on other subjects (Figure 4), such as astronomy, optical illusions, and conic sections though most of them are not available anymore due to the destruction of the library of Alexandria.

Without being absolutely certain, it is said that when Ptolemy asked Euclid for an easier way to learn Geometry, he replied that "there is no royal road to Geometry" (Proclus, Annotated principles). Euclid believed that the study of mathematics should aim at knowledge and not at a material gain. In Stovaius' “Anthologion” it is stated that when a student asked Euclid what he would gain if he learned geometry, Euclid asked his servant to give his student three obolus because he needed to gain something from what he learned (Arabatzis et al. 1999).

Euclid is known as the father of Geometry as he is the first to give Geometry an unsurpassed logical rigor by introducing the axiomatic method (the basic principle of constructing a proof science). In his thirteen-volume textbook called the “Elements”, which will be presented in

the following chapter, Euclid conducted a rigorous, thoughtful, logical march through plane geometry, number theory, old form of algebra and then, also solid geometry (i.e., geometry of three dimensions). In fact, Elements transformed the way mathematics was perceived amongst scientists. Euclid's Elements even assisted young Abraham Lincoln to "fine-tune his mind"; Lincoln advocated how it was Euclid who showed him what "demonstrate" actually meant, which was crucial for his law studies (Dunham 1991). Euclid's work influenced all kinds of great thinkers, not just mathematicians such as Alfred North Whitehead, Baruch Spinoza, and Bertrand Russell, etc.

Figure 3: Euclid's explaining geometry in the school of Athens- Painting by Raffaello 1509

Euclid's Bibliography

- Elements
- Data
- On Division Figures of
- Phaenomena
- Optics
- Porisms
- Conics
- Surface Loci
- Fallacies
- Catoptrics
- Sectio Canonis

Figure 4: Euclid's Bibliography

3.1 Euclid's Elements

As for geometry, this term literally means the measurement of the earth (i.e., geo = $\gamma\eta$ = Earth + metry = $\mu\epsilon\tau\rho\acute{\omega}$ = to measure); what now is called "surveying" arose from the practical needs of the agricultural people of ancient Mesopotamia and Egypt because they had to measure out in plots of land. In Egypt, the annual flooding of the Nile, which fertilized the land, meant - as it still does today - that the boundaries of the fields had to be redrawn as they were washed away. Early methods of surveying space were also used in construction. The ancient temples, roads, and canals of Egypt and Mesopotamia attest to the geometric skills their builders had acquired. Records have survived showing how advanced they were. None of this, however, was geometry as we know it today. The word was coined by the Greeks because it was, they who turned the practical rules of measurement into an orderly branch of mathematics. The earliest mathematical proofs are attributed to Thales of Miletus, who lived around 585 B.C., while Euclid was already at work in 300 B.C. Euclid taught in Alexandria, located at the western end of the Nile Delta. The city had been enlarged by Alexander the Great in 332 B.C. and given its new name, and quickly developed into the largest center of Greek influence outside Greece - what is now called "Hellenistic culture." (Boyer, 1956)

The Elements is a thirteen-volume textbook and probably the most famous textbook of all time, after the Bible. In these books Euclid took the mathematical knowledge of his time, arranged it, and presented it in an orderly and logical manner. The Elements was considered the most perfect example of a theory in which conclusions are drawn from assumptions in a systematic way (i.e., a "deductive theory") (K.E.ΕΠ.ΕΚ, 2001). In his proofs he used all the dialectical methods, the divisive one for finding the species, the definitive one in the essential reasons, the evidential one in the transition from the fundamental principles to the demanded ones, and the analytical one in the transition in reverse, from the demanded ones to the fundamental principles (K.E.ΕΠ.ΕΚ, 2001). Euclidean geometry is usually divided into plane geometry, which deals with figures and constructions in two or fewer dimensions such as the circle, the ellipse, the line, and the point, and solid or three-dimensional geometry, which deals with three-dimensional figures such as the sphere, the polyhedron, and the ellipsoid.

The propositions of the "Elements" are divided into two categories, theorems and problems. Theorems are the propositions, which seek to find the truth, i.e., their proof, demonstrably.

Problems are the propositions in which the construction of a certain geometric figure is requested.

After the proof of each theorem, Euclid repeats his statement and adds: “ὅπερ ἔδει δεῖξαι”. At the end of each problem, he adds the phrase: “ὅπερ ἔδει ποιῆσαι”. In the first book of Euclid's Elements, 23 definitions, 5 postulates, and 9 common notions are given priority - Aristotle prefers the term axiom instead of proposition and notion. The 47th proposition is the Pythagorean theorem. The second book contains 14 theorems and problems, in which mainly geometrically fundamental identities of algebra are considered. The eleventh problem is the golden section theorem. In the third book, which contains 37 theorems and problems, the properties of the circle are examined, since 11 definitions are given, in which it is determined when circles are equal, when a line is a tangent to a circle, etc. In the fourth book, after seven definitions are introduced, the construction of the simplest regular polygons and the writing and description of them in a circle in 16 sentences is considered. In the fifth book, 18 definitions are prefixed, followed by 25 theorems, in which properties of analogies are investigated. The fourth definition is called the continuity axiom by the younger ones and is used in higher mathematics. In the sixth book, five definitions are prefixed, followed by 33 theorems, in which similar schemes are investigated. The seventh, eighth, and ninth books contain the elements of number theory. The tenth book is the most extensive of all. It contains four definitions and 115 theorems. It is the most difficult of all the books of the "Elements". It is a question of whether there are few mathematicians in the world who understand it. Besides, there is no unanimity among the experts as to the purpose of this book, which, according to some, is intended to show that the harmony of the Universe is governed by symmetry and asymmetry, which, when combined, produce harmony, as it is held to be understood by the Platonic doctrine. The eleventh, twelfth, and thirteenth books are on stereometry. In the eleventh book, 28 definitions are given, which define solid shapes, followed by 39 theorems, in which prisms are considered. The pyramid, the cone, the cylinder, and the sphere are treated in 18 theorems of the twelfth book, while the study and registration of the five regular polyhedral in a sphere are treated in the thirteenth and last book of the Elements, which also contains 18 theorems.

In Euclid's Elements, one can point out the various types of inversions, both the simplest and the most complex, and which of the theorems have inversions and which do not. Particularly

noteworthy are the parsimony and order observed in the connection of the preceding theorems with the subsequent ones, and the force with which each of them was formulated. Euclid uses the following four methods of proof in the Elements: The synthetic method, deduction to inconclusive, the analytic method, and perfect induction (or recursive reasoning). In general, the synthetic method is the one most commonly used in mathematical science. Aristotle calls it deictic or categorical.

Figure 5: Oxyrhynchus papyrus (P.Oxy. I 29) showing a fragment of Euclid's Elements. It is referred to "Proposition 5 of the Book 2 of Elements". - Public domain

4. Digital humanities as a field of research

A synchronous renaissance phase is claimed to be experienced by the field of humanities because of the rise of digital humanities. Digital humanities is identified as the “intersection of computational methods and humanities materials” (McCarty 2005; Drucker 2021); this could be understood as the use of digital tools to investigate humanities resources. In the case of the latter, they may be analogue form or born-digital (i.e., resources already created in digital format without having an analogue counterpart, such as a Word document or a PowerPoint presentation). Every project revolving around digital humanities includes three basic components, namely “materials, processing, and presentation” (Drucker 2021) and involves methods that may be unusual in the world of traditional humanities.

As materials are considered the items to be investigated as digital representations with the use of technology. This calls for data modelling, mediation/remediation, file creation, metadata production for use and description, and other considerations such as licenses, sustainability, rights, etc. (Drucker 2021). For example, in order for the Onassis Foundation to digitize the poems of the poet K. P. Kavafis, it had to acquire the rights of the poems and transform them into digital files. The way in which materials become digital is very important as it defines the size, needs as well as limitations of each digital project. Processing of the materials is also vital within the project as different technological tools and methods may be opaque to the researcher or difficult to use; thus, additional training or collaboration between two different fields of study is deemed necessary. For instance, when the European-funded project called “Elexis” was forming the creation of a database was needed therefore data scientists were hired to work along with lexicographers; not only was interdisciplinary work promoted but also the exchange of knowledge between the two groups was achieved. Once a project is complete, it is often presented online in order to encourage learning and acquisition of new information. Depending on the nature of the project, it can be published either on a blog, website, or even an application, etc. The way the final product is presented can affect how the research is received by the audience and what the end result is. Most of the time projects are aimed at the academic audience but nowadays they are also designed to attract a general audience (i.e., public humanities) (Smulyan, 2020). One example of a final product that is dedicated to a non-specific target audience is the “Hidden Cities” by the University of Exeter; a series of apps where historians work closely with cities in order to

create a guided tour with hidden passages and unpopular information derived from historical sources. The product is free and is enjoyed by many tourists who have the opportunity to have their own tourist guide, who is actually an avatar of that time.

In order for the aforementioned projects to come to life, some fundamental activities/steps took place. In particular, these include “mediation/remediation, datafication/modelling, presentation/display, sustainability/preservation” (Drucker 2021). The first process includes either transforming analogue materials such as manuscripts and archaeological ruins, into a digital format or producing and later using born-digital products; taking information in form A into form B is called *remediation*. Born digital material is very often mediated and each of the formats plays a crucial role in its use. For example, a .tiff image is very important for researching the materials of a painting but requires a lot of storage space, while a .jpg image is suitable for storage but is of lower quality. As far as datafication is concerned, this activity includes “abstracting discrete values from a phenomenon or artifact” (Drucker 2021). With datafication automated processes can be achieved, such as counting, comparing, making statistical assessments, etc. Thus, materials or phenomena such as the height of mountains, a list of churches, or ships may be quantifiable. The use of data modeling helps in datafication and thus in the description and representation of materials or artifacts. Once materials can be calculated somehow, automation of the process (e.g., counting, analyzing, comparing, etc.) using a machine or program is imminent. For example, the ArcGIS Pro program can be used to create maps with two-dimensional data or to compare them based on their similarities and differences. After the data processing, the analysis takes over and information extraction becomes possible. Once the analysis is complete, the presentation/ display of the end product follows. Every research presentation has a narrative that guides how the data is displayed. When presenting research results, the simplest interface design involves decisions about the order and selection of what is important and what is not, what should be displayed and what should be hidden; every decision should be in harmony with the purposes of each project. Last but not least, the “sustainability/preservation” of the final project is crucial for the continuation and maintenance of the end result. The institutional setting in which the project originates and is executed, the available resources and capabilities (cost and labor), and other project-specific criteria (e.g., the evolution of technology) influence the initial design selection (e.g., the intellectual property involved, privacy and protection issues, and the

regulations to which the work is subject). In the case of “Hidden Cities” project of the University of Exeter, for instance, the project leader, Professor Fabrizio Nevola (2022) suggests that the final product should have basic features such as videos and music so that the application requires the minimal features of a phone and avoids the fear of any phone updates. Sustainability also considers the environmental and human rights costs associated with digital work in a highly connected world. Creating and maintaining any digital project is expensive. Therefore, planning and maintenance should be considered at the design stage of any project.

5. Euclid's Elements as a source for research

The manuscripts of antiquity have always been a product of modern study, whether or not they contain a digital component. Euclid's Elements, in particular, have been the subject of various academic investigations with different objectives. In this chapter, three important projects are presented and their contribution to science is acknowledged.

The first digital project to be presented is Oliver Byrne's Euclid "The first six books of Elements"² (1847). The project was undertaken by Nicholas Rougeux, who is a designer and data artist focusing in web and UX design. Byrne's 1847 edition of the first six books is notable for its use of vivid drawings to illustrate proofs, rather than using letters to mark angles, edges, and shapes. His version was one of the first books produced with such elaborate coloring and combined with the intricate diagrams, it was an outstanding publishing achievement for the time. It is still an outstanding work of art today. According to Rougeux, the project has a didactic purpose and in particular, the website was designed to bring Byrne's living edition to life by making it accessible to a contemporary audience by putting the entire book online in a flexible format that is as close to the original as possible. For each diagram, the originals have been recreated, and verified that the relationships and dimensions conform to Euclid's geometric rules. Clickable shapes have been added to the proofs associated with each diagram to make it easier to grasp the shapes being referenced.

Figure 6: Properties of a triangle – Illustration by Oliver Byrne

² You may visit the website here: <https://www.c82.net/euclid/>

The website with focuses on making Euclid's ideas and theories accessible to the common audience by using a user-friendly interface. It also creates the aesthetic of the book from which it was inspired, and provides an interactive environment for learning, practicing, and testing. It is also multilingual, which encourages the engagement of people from all over the world. In general, this project can be treated as an idea that encompasses digital humanities concentrating on didacts, teaching, and less on research. Yet, this task indicates how multifaceted the field of digital humanities is.

A second project related to Euclid's Elements is designed by Dimitrios Mourmouras³. This website has been constructed in HTML format with the aim of being accessible to everyone. This design allows further researchers to investigate various terms and words by clicking on the "Search" button. The project is relatively newly available, having been published in 2020 and restoring Euclid's elements from Euaggelos Stamatis in 1953. The website is divided into two main parts: the research-based part and the book-based part. The first part takes a linguistic approach and provides the user with terms and concepts along with dictionaries, language tools and other versions in Modern Greek. This part facilitates the researcher's work by bringing together all the important linguistic information in one place, but could concentrate the research of scholars who are not linguists. In the second part of the website, the books are divided and include "Definitions" and "Propositions" sections. The website itself is an interesting collaboration between digital humanities and linguistics.

ΣΤΟΙΧΕΙΩΝ Α'-ΙΓ'

ΕΡΕΥΝΑ Α' Β' Γ' Δ' Ε' ΣΤ' Ζ' Η' Θ' Ι' ΙΑ' ΙΒ' ΙΓ'

Ἡ ἀποθησαύρισις τῶν «Στοιχείων»

Κατεβάστε ἐδῶ τὸ ἀρχεῖο σὲ μορφή EXCEL

Οἱ 2288 λέξεις ποὺ ὑπάρχουν στὰ «Στοιχεῖα» μὲ τὶς συχνοτητές τους. (Συνολικά 123004 λέξεις)

Ταξινομήστε ἀλφαβητικά ἢ κατὰ συχνότητα κάνοντας «κλικ» στὴν ἐπιγραφίδα τοῦ πίνακος!

α/α	ΛΕΞΗ	Συχνότητα
1	καί	5947
2	τό	5797
3	ἢ	5190
4	πρός	3820
5	ἀρα	3809
6	τῶν	2749
7	τῆς	2643
8	ἀπό	2400
9	δέ	2380
10	ὑπό	2351

³ You may visit the website here: <http://www.physics.ntua.gr/mourmouras/euclid/>

Figure 7: Frequency word list in Euclid's Elements

As a final project dedicated to Euclid's Elements, it is part of the Perseus digital library provided by Tufts University. The Perseus Digital Library Project has been studying what happens when libraries go online since it began planning in 1985. This topic is more important than ever today, 20 years later, as new publication media and millions of books are converted to digital formats. As part of the Perseus experiment, researchers are exploring the possibilities and difficulties of digital collections in a networked environment. Perseus maintains a website that showcases the collections and services that have been created over the years as a result of the university's research. Many of the collections scholars have created, as well as the code for the digital library system, are now openly accessible. One of these is Euclid's Elements by Sir Thomas L. Heath⁴. Euclid's books have been divided into volumes and their respective chapters (i.e., definitions, postulates, common notions, and propositions). Users can browse through the various chapters in both Ancient Greek and English and when clicked, are taken to the translation and grammatical analysis of each word in Ancient Greek. The website also offers XML-TEI encoding, which facilitates further research. As for the XML-TEI encoding of the manuscripts, it is important to note that the coding needs to be further enriched and extended, as there are some points that need to be improved and developed. It could be argued that in this project Euclid's masterpiece is treated like a random text that has no meaning or value, but only a linguistic meaning. Therefore, it is important to experiment with this piece of work and try to reinvent parts of it by implementing the TEI encoding system on a deeper level.

The aforementioned projects are some attempts to represent and encode Euclid's work and make it accessible to everyone. Like any project, they have their limitations and points of improvement. For this reason, my project will attempt to fill in some of these gaps and pose further questions to the scientific community, and in particular to the field of text encoding.

⁴ You may visit the website here:

<http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0085%3Abook%3D1%3Atype%3DProp%3Anumber%3D4>

6. Methodology

This chapter presents the methodological conventions adapted for this project. In this section, the empirical part, which includes the data collection and the steps to encode it, is presented. In addition, an attempt is made to provide an explanation of the corresponding tags that were used to interpret and highlight the content, which is the aim of this work. This project does not attempt to calculate the frequency of the various tags, as the main focus is on the semantic representation of the data and not on the possible quantitative side. The following sections describe the data collection and analysis process in detail.

First, it was important to choose a suitable program for TEI transcription. Therefore, the program oXygen was the most suitable for this project, as it is recommended by the TEI Consortium and includes a validator that checks the transcription against the TEI guidelines. Once the program is installed, the encryption process begins. The transcription process has started by stating the contributors and members of this transcription along with the necessary TEI components regarding the edition of the book in `<teiHeader>` section (see Fig. 7).

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<?xml-model href="http://www.tei-c.org/release/xml/tei/custom/schema/relaxng/tei_all.rng"?>
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"
  xmlns:tei="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"
  xmlns:dbo="http://dipedia.org/ontology/"
  >
  <teiHeader>
    <fileDesc>
      <titleStmt>
        <title>Euclidis Elementa</title>
        <author>Euclid</author>
      </titleStmt>
      <editionStmt>
        <edition>J.L. Heiberg</edition>
      </editionStmt>
      <respStmt>
        <resp>Transcription</resp>
        <persName>Prof. Christos Papatheodorou</persName>
        <persName>Dimitra Grigoriou</persName>
        <orgName>Athens University of Economics and Business (AUEB)</orgName>
      </respStmt>
      <resp>Encoding</resp>
        <persName>Dimitra Grigoriou</persName>
        <orgName>Athens University of Economics and Business (AUEB)</orgName>
      </respStmt>
      </editionStmt>
      <publicationStmt>
        <publisher>B. G. Teubner</publisher>
        <authority>Perseus.edu: Perseus Digital Library</authority>
        <pubPlace>Leipzig</pubPlace>
        <date>1883-1888</date>
        <availability>
          <licence target="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/us/">Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 United States
        </licence>
        </availability>
      </publicationStmt>
      <sourceDesc>
        <msDesc>
          <msIdentifier>
            <settlement>Perseus.edu</settlement>
            <repository>Perseus Digital Library</repository>
          </msIdentifier>
          <msContents>
            <msItem><title>Euclidis Elementa: Book 1</title></msItem>
          </msContents>
        </msDesc>
      </sourceDesc>
    </fileDesc>
  </teiHeader>
```

Figure 8: Structure of TeiHeader

First, for the purpose of encoding, it was important to set up an identity (i.e., `xml:id`) for each of the documents to be transcribed. The id is composed of five chunks separated by full

stops; these are namely the title of the book, the volume, the type of section to be encoded followed by the respected number, and the language of the transcribed text (i.e., ancient Greek). This is how *elem.1.definition.3.ell*, *elem.1.cn.4.ell*, *elem.1.post.4.ell* and *elem.1.propo.47.ell* are formed. Once the individual ids are set it was time to encode the parts of the book in the TEI document (see Fig. 8).

```
<body>
  <div n="1" type="book" org="uniform" sample="complete">
    <div n="2" type="Definitions" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [125 lines]
    <div n="3" type="Common_notions" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [10 lines]
    <div n="4" type="Postulates" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [6 lines]
    <div n="5" type="Propositions" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [1838 lines]
  </div>
</body>
```

Figure 9: Divisions of the first book of Elements

In the above figure, you can see that there are four divisions named after the particular concept they describe, nested within the "book" division; this means that all four divisions are part of a larger division (i.e., the book). Each of the respected departments can be expanded into sub-departments containing each expression separately (see Figure 10). This contains the separate ID together with the number of the expression and its type.

```
<body>
  <div n="1" type="book" org="uniform" sample="complete">
    <div n="2" type="Definitions" org="uniform" sample="complete">
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.1.ell" n="1" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.2.ell" n="2" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.3.ell" n="3" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.4.ell" n="4" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.5.ell" n="5" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.6.ell" n="6" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [6 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.7.ell" n="7" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.8.ell" n="8" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.9.ell" n="9" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.10.ell" n="10" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.11.ell" n="11" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.12.ell" n="12" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.13.ell" n="13" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.14.ell" n="14" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.15.ell" n="15" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.16.ell" n="16" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.17.ell" n="17" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.18.ell" n="18" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.19.ell" n="19" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.20.ell" n="20" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.21.ell" n="21" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.22.ell" n="22" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [5 lines]
      <div xml:id="elem.l.definition.23.ell" n="23" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [4 lines]
    </div>
    <div n="3" type="Common notions" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [10 lines]
    <div n="4" type="Postulates" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [6 lines]
    <div n="5" type="Propositions" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [2646 lines]
  </div>
</body>
```

Figure 10: Examples of expanded subdivisions of Elements

Since the goal of this project is to encode the content of the book, it was deemed useful to add identification markers and additional tags for the entities to be highlighted, such as terms, names, intertextual references, and so on. Especially for definitions, an external ontology - namely DBpedia - was implemented to enrich the existing schema. This was achieved by inserting the @ ref tag and the corresponding link, as can be seen in Figure 11:

```
<div xml:id="elem.l.definition.1.ell" n="1" type="Definition" org="uniform" sample="complete">
  <p>
    <term xml:id="def01" target="http://el.dbpedia.org/resource/Σημείο">σημείον</term>
    ἔστιν, <gloss target="#def01">οὐ μέρος οὐθέν</gloss>.
  </p>
</div>
```

Figure 11: Examples of entities linked with external databases

An additional feature added, especially in the definitions section, is the component that offers an explanation of the unknown term. In the case of elements, it was decided to use the tag `<term></term>`, every time Euclid introduces a new term, even though according to the TEI P5 guidelines, this tag is preferably suitable for dictionaries. Each term introduced by Euclid is accompanied by another tag (i.e., `<gloss></gloss>`), which is an important component because it defines the term. With the 26 definitions, Euclid thus establishes 35 terms with their respective glosses. In encoding the definitions, it was important to transcribe each term with a different ID so that it could be used each time Euclid referred to a particular term. In this way, a mapping between entities is achieved.

The "Common notions" and "Postulates" sections are constructed in a similar manner. In these sections, the tag (i.e., `<rs></rs>`), has been added to each paragraph because it signifies a referring string according to the TEI P5 guidelines (see Fig. 12). As for the content of the two sections, the terms are tagged and assigned to the corresponding entities to which the terms refer, such as "εὐθεῖαι", "σημεῖον", "κύκλον", etc. In this way, the entities are linked together, form a semantic web and promote intertextuality.

```
<body>
  <div n="1" type="book" org="uniform" sample="complete">
    <div n="2" type="Definitions" org="uniform" sample="complete"> [125 lines]
      <div n="3" type="Common_notions" org="uniform" sample="complete">
        <p><rs xml:id="cn01" type="common_notion">τὰ τῶ αὐτῷ ἴσα καὶ ἀλλήλοις ἐστὶν ἴσα</rs>.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn02" type="common_notion">καὶ ἐὰν ἴσοις ἴσα προστεθῆ, τὰ ὅλα ἐστὶν ἴσα</rs>.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn03" type="common_notion">καὶ ἐὰν ἀπὸ ἴσων ἴσα ἀφαιρεθῆ, τὰ καταλειπόμενά ἐστὶν ἴσα</rs>.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn04" type="common_notion">καὶ ἐὰν ἀνίσοις ἴσα προστεθῆ, τὰ ὅλα ἐστὶν ἀνίσα</rs>.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn05" type="common_notion">καὶ τὰ τοῦ αὐτοῦ διπλάσια ἴσα ἀλλήλοις ἐστὶν.</rs></p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn06" type="common_notion">καὶ τὰ τοῦ αὐτοῦ ἡμίση ἴσα ἀλλήλοις ἐστὶν.</rs></p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn07" type="common_notion">καὶ τὰ τοῦ αὐτοῦ ἐπ' ἀλλήλα ἴσα ἀλλήλοις ἐστὶν.</rs></p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn08" type="common_notion">καὶ τὸ ὅλον τοῦ μέρους μείζον ἐστὶν.</rs></p>
        <p><rs xml:id="cn09" type="common_notion">καὶ δύο <term ref="#def03">εὐθεῖαι</term> χωρίον οὐ περιέχουσιν.</rs></p>
      </div>
      <div n="4" type="Postulates" org="uniform" sample="complete">
        <p><rs xml:id="post1" type="postulate">Ἡτῆσθα ἀπὸ παντός <term ref="#def01">σημεῖου</term> ἐπὶ πᾶν <term ref="#def02">κύκλον</term> ἵσταναι.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="post2" type="postulate">καὶ πεπερασμένην <term ref="def03">εὐθεῖαν</term> κατὰ τὸ συνεχές ἐπ' <term ref="#def04">εὐθεῖαν</term> ἵσταναι.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="post3" type="postulate">καὶ παντὶ <term ref="#def14">κέντρῳ</term> καὶ διαστήματι <term ref="#def05">κύκλου</term> ἵσταναι.</p>
        <p><rs xml:id="post4" type="postulate">καὶ πάσας τὰς <term ref="#def08">ὀρθὰς γωνίας</term> ἴσας ἀλλήλαις εἶναι.</rs>
        <p><rs xml:id="post5" type="postulate">καὶ ἐὰν εἰς δύο <term ref="def03">εὐθείας</term> <term ref="def03">εὐθεῖαι</term> τε...

```

Figure 12: Structure of Common notions and Postulates

As for the Proposition section, the structure of the previous sections has been retained, with some additions deemed important. These include, in particular, the introduction of line breaks (i.e., `<lb/>`) when the original text ended, and the separation of sections with respect to their content. Within the `<rs></rs>` tags, parts denoting the structure of Euclid's argument, such as enunciation, setting out, specification, construction, proof, and conclusion, were given different IDs (see Figure 13).

```
<div xml:id="elem.1.propo.1.e11" n="1" type="Proposition" org="uniform" sample="complete">
  <div xml:id="enunci1" type="enunciation">
    <p>
      <lb n="1"/>ἐπι τῆς δοθείσης <term ref="#def03">εὐθείας</term> πεπερασμένης <term ref="#def24"><term ref="#def26">πίγμων</term> ἰσόλευρον</term> συστήσασθαι.
    </p>
  </div>
  <div xml:id="e001" type="setting_out">
    <p>
      <lb n="2"/>
      <lb n="3"/>ἴστω ἡ δοθεῖσα <term ref="#def03">εὐθεῖα</term> πεπερασμένη ἢ <name xml:id="ln001">AB</name>.
    </p>
  </div>
  <div xml:id="d001" type="specification">
    <p>
      <lb n="4"/>ἕστ' εἴ ἐπι τῆς <name ref="#ln001">AB</name> <term ref="#def03">εὐθείας</term> <term ref="#def24"><term ref="#def26">πίγμων</term> ἰσόλευρον</term> συστήσασθαι
      <lb rend="displayNum" n="5"/>
    </p>
  </div>
</div>
```

Figure 13: Structure of enunciation and setting out in Propositions

In order to reproduce the text accurately, it was important to also insert and retain the line numbers established by the editor, even though they do not necessarily correspond to the lines of the text. The line numbers have been expressed in a separate line by reproducing the number referred to in the edition. As for the content, similar to the Common Notions and Postulates, each time a term is already introduced, for this reason, an `@ref` tag with the appropriate ID has been used.

In the section of Propositions Euclid is using names to make concrete the notions that he is introducing in his manuscripts. These features are important to be encoded as it assists researchers to a collective approach towards the investigation of each term. To achieve this, the tag `<name></name>` has been inserted before the name of each element following by a unique identifier. In the following table (i.e., Table 1) it can be seen the name of the element, how its respected id has been formed followed by an example.

Term	Term prefix	Example
line	<code>xml:id="lnXXX"</code>	<code><name xml:id="ln001">AB</name></code>
point	<code>xml:id="ptXXX"</code>	<code><name xml:id="pt002">B</name></code>

triangle	xml:id="triXXX"	<name xml:id="tri009"> ΒΓΖ</name>
circle	xml:id="ceXXX"	<name xml:id="ce006"> ΚΛΗ</name>
angle	xml:id="angXXX"	<name xml:id="ang020"> ΑΓΒ</name>
parallelogram	xml:id="parallXXX"	<name xml:id="parall012"> ΖΕΓΗ</name>
rectangle	xml:id="rectXXX"	<name xml:id="rect001 "> ΑΒΓΔ</name>

Table 1: Structure of terms in TEI

At this point it is vital to mention that when Euclid is referring to the same element in a Proposition but with a different structure of the name, for instance the line AB he calls it BA, the identifier is not changed as it is still linked with the same entity. In this case the use of tag `@ref` is implemented which denotes the anaphoric characteristic. In addition, there are instances in which Euclid mentions a term which he has not yet defined in his Definitions section of Book 1; some examples are “διάμετρος”, “ὑποτείνουσης”, “παραλληλόγραμμον”, etc. Such cases are marked solely with the tag `<term></term>` without being linked to an external LOD or a definition provided by Euclid in his first book. A final element that was encoded in the Proposition sections was the concept of intertextuality which is defined as the reference of other sections within one text – in our case the section of Propositions. This was accomplished by using the `<rs></rs>` tag to the referred element followed by the `@ref` tag which includes the part that indicates where this phrase was originally mentioned (i.e., definition, proposition, common notion, postulate) preceded by the `@type` tag which states the type of the `<rs>` (see Fig. 14)

```
<rs ref="#elem.1.propo.14.e11" type="reference_proposal">ἐν' <term ref="#def03">εὐθείας</term> ἄρα ἐστὶν ἡ <name ref="#ln286">ΓΑ</name> τῆ <name ref="#ln293">ΑΗ</name></rs>.
```

Figure 14: Structure of intertextuality in Propositions

7. Discussion of the encoding process

TEI is a schema that allows researchers to create files in a machine-readable format. Like any digital edition, TEI is suitable for encoding because it provides all the necessary tools in its format. This is the reason why TEI was chosen for this project. Indeed, the project refers to written documents that were originally transcribed in a rather hasty way, without respecting their semantic value, and through this attempt, there would be a reappraisal with the tools provided by TEI.

The encoding process at hand was not something that happened immediately. Long discussions and emails were exchanged with various experts in this field to reach this result. In general, from a purely practical point of view, this project was designed with a lesser “TEI-centric” perspective. The reason why this strategy was followed is that no single technology can usually provide its users with what is needed unless something trivial has happened or compromises are part of the process. TEI is an excellent tool to encode texts as it has been done already but the trivial part begins once the elements needed to be focused on are set; this was solved by adding tags to the plain transcribed text. Nevertheless, just as when dealing with people, places, monuments, archeological artifacts, or other entities in a document, it is usually useful to separate these areas. The text, namely, rests on one domain; the entities, such as a reference to another text, a name of an object, a geometric form, etc., rest on another. This was the first decision made before dealing with the first book of Elements (i.e., to start with two domains, the text that talks about things, and the things that are each modeled and encoded separately). The following step was to link the two domains: the domain of the text and the domain of the “things” (i.e., entities). This link was achieved in two different ways; the first one occurred by identifying the appellation of an entity, for example, τρίγωνο, τριγώνου, or any other inflected form or synonym, and wrapping these versions in the same add tag; then, adding a @ref attribute pointing to the text when this entity is being explained and has been already defined by a unique ID. The entities linked to the text are also modeled and consequently, in a different way. Within the encoding process of the entities, an external LOD ontology (i.e., DBpedia) was adopted. This is how the entities are linked but also enriched with the information provided by the external source. In a philosophical way of speaking these “appellations” (i.e., the entities rest on a different domain) rest on a sort of Platonic hyperuranium, while their eidola cannot be known,

researchers try to approximate their description by providing a formal model which best describes them according to researchers' perspective and objectives.

In the case of Euclid's first book, the importance of its contents was the idea that motivated the writing of this work. Preserving and highlighting every significant value of his work was the primary goal of this work. The encoding process took a great deal of time and concentration. The final product is something that could help the scientific community in their research, but there are also a few elements that need to be discussed in the following chapter dedicated to the limitations of this project.

8. Limitations of the project

In this chapter, the project's limitations will be acknowledged.

The present project could be seen as an experiment in how the future books of the Elements could be encoded using the TEI format. The encoding of the first book itself is by definition a limitation, since Euclid's entire masterpiece is not complete; however, this has been done due to time constraints. Furthermore, the fact that there is no ontology devoted exclusively to geometry in which terms could be clearly defined and explained by scientists indicates that there is a gap in this area that could be the occasion for future research. In the context of this task, it appears that some elements are linked to an external linked open ontology (LOD), while others are not.

Another limitation considered important for the research purpose was the source of the text. To be precise, the first book was not studied from its original text or a copy of it, but from the already transcribed version available in the Perseus Library. This has led to several problems in the transcription. First, some parts are not properly attributed, so a researcher might have the impression that they are missing, which is not true. Also, the original or copy versions might help transcribe more stylistic or written features that could be useful for philological and biographical research. Re-transcription of the already transcribed text lacks the editorial component/contribution.

The TEI standard is one that has helped us approach the connection between entities and text. In many cases, these are practices and policies where TEI has many "gray areas" in terms of its uses and approaches. There have been times when TEI has seemed more like a cage than a tool because of its overlapping structures and limited examples of how to implement certain tags. An example of this is the use of `<term></tags>` and `<gloss></gloss>` tags primarily for dictionaries. However, the case of Euclid's Elements is a special one, as it is a mixture of dictionary (i.e., by including definitions) and text. However, the use of such a tag is not mandated in the TEI guidelines. Therefore, the need for further extensions and changes in TEI is suggested for the future.

In summary, the encoding of Euclid's elements is still being explored and more details may emerge once the entire collection is complete. The attributes and relationships formed could

later be expressed in an RDF or RDF* model so that an enriched LOD can be formed. As mentioned earlier, the project itself is still under exploration and provides a solid foundation for further research for individuals specializing in the field of humanities and digital humanities.

9. Conclusion

The emergence of Digital Humanities as a field of study paves the way for a transition from traditional research methods to modern and technology-based methods. This transition requires not only close collaboration between two different fields of study - namely, the field of traditional studies and the field of information technology - but also the invention of new programs and standards that will connect two worlds. In the case of written documents, the rise of the TEI standard from the XML markup language has proven essential for encoding documents in a machine-readable format.

The TEI standard has become an indispensable tool in the academic community and especially in digital editions. Through the TEI Consortium, changes and extensions are added every year to enrich this tool and eliminate unclear areas during the encoding process. The literary work of this thesis was also coded using this standard. As can be seen from the literature review, many similar projects, whether in ancient Greek or English, have been undertaken using the TEI or other digital tools to make a digitized version of Euclid's Elements available online. However, none of these projects reviewed have fully captured both the format and the essence of Euclid's work.

The need for a better encoding approach for the ancient text, taking into account its semantic value, as well as investigating whether the TEI standard is sufficient for encoding mathematical texts, were the primary research goals of this work. During the encoding process, we found that elements of the TEI such as, `<term></term>` should be extended and implemented in cases where new terms and their respective definitions can be found, and not only within the concept of a dictionary. In addition, names of instances of mathematical concepts such as angles, lines, points, etc. should be encoded under the `<name></name>` tag as they fulfil this condition and designate the term. In addition, the use of tags should be expanded so that more lines of a text can be included in that text. Finally, the use of open source Linked Data was a very important decision, as it promotes the concept of semantic network and provides a base system with which statements can be linked together and form knowledge groups.

At the very end, I would like to emphasize how much the current research and the writing of this research project have improved my knowledge and understanding of the somewhat

underestimated phenomenon of text encoding mathematical concepts. Moreover, the process of data collection and the research itself have inspired me to develop further projects that shed light on the various facets of TEI and its application to different literary works. My interest in digitization processes in general, originally sparked in the corpora-based lecture of my first master's program at the University of Vienna, has greatly deepened through research and ongoing discussions with experts in the field of digital humanities. Ultimately, this experimental research process has proven to be a valuable learning journey.

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